

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

2024-25 Seed Grant Program Final Report

Precise Localization and Measurement of Slow Slip Events in Central Cascadia with InSAR

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Crescent Project Report – CRESCENT SEED GRANT PROGRAM 2024-2025
Precise Localization and Measurement of Slow Slip Events in Central Cascadia
with InSAR

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Performance Period: June 3rd, 2025 to April 30th, 2026

I proposed to study earthquake hazards in Central Cascadia by analyzing slow slip events (SSEs) through InSAR data. SSEs manifest as large-scale distortions of the Earth's surface. These seismically silent events can significantly affect seismic hazards by altering their surrounding stress field. Geodetic observations of SSEs have mostly been made using the GNSS network. However, the network's sparsity often hampers precise subsurface slip localization. InSAR's ability to provide dense surface measurements, especially its sensitivity to vertical movements, is pivotal for determining the SSE zone at depth. Our objective is to produce spatially dense SSE deformation maps that, in conjunction with other existing measurements such as the GPS and seismic data, will enable the precise localization and measurement of slip distribution in the Cascadia subduction zone.

1. Major Goals and Objectives of the Project

The major goals and objectives of this project were to: (1) collect and process existing SAR archive that cover the study area, (2) analyze the 2016 winter Central Cascadia SSE, (3) analysis of the 2018 and 2020 winter Central Cascadia SSEs and (4) extract interSSE velocity, and finally (5) localization of the SSE at depth through slow slip geodetic modeling.

2. Accomplishments Under These Goals

Task 1: Data Collection and Processing

Figure 1: Sentinel-1 and ALOS-2 acquisitions during the study period. The grey bars indicate identified periods of slow slip events in Central Cascadia via tremor logs.

We processed 757 ascending Sentinel-1A/B frames (frame 137-147, track 35) and 643 descending Sentinel-1A/B frames (frame 438 – 448, track 13) using Geocoded SLC flow from the open source package SWEETS (<https://github.com/isce-framework/sweets>). We also processed ALOS-2 acquisitions during the study period, however, we find the temporal coverage of ALOS-2 insufficient to recover the SSE events (Figure 1).

Tasks 2 & 3: Analysis of the Feb 2016, 2018 and 2020 winter SSEs.

Figure 2: We identified 6 SSE in Central Cascadia during the study period and focus on the first 5 due to temporal coverage of the SAR acquisitions.

We first analyzed tremor activity between 2015 and 2025 using the Pacific Northwest Seismic Network Tremor Catalog and identified six slow-slip events (SSEs; Figure 2). We focused our analysis on the first five events because they had better temporal coverage and more coherent spatial extent. These five events include the previously proposed 2016, 2018, and 2020 winter Central Cascadia SSEs. The final event appears to be segmented in both space and time and was therefore excluded because of limited temporal coverage following the event.

To retrieve deformation maps associated with Central Cascadia SSEs, we applied the redundant stacking method developed by Zheng et al. (2021). This approach is designed to reduce atmospheric artifacts and decorrelation noise by combining multiple interferograms. We further screened the interferograms using criteria based on temporal baseline and data coverage. The resulting deformation maps are shown in Figure 3. For the first SSE, 110 interferograms were used in the stacking process out of 494 possible interferograms. For the second SSE, 406 out of 1800 were used; for the third, 403 out of 2277; for the fourth, 498 out of 2732; and for the fifth, 379 out of 2064.

Figure 3: stacking result for the 5 SSEs in Central Cascadia.

We further combined all five mini-SSE stacks into one stack to generate an average deformation map of all the SSEs in the study period. The result is shown in Figure 4. The retrieved deformation pattern is broadly consistent with what we expected from a simple forward model. Specifically the profile lines show the characteristic uplift near the coast and the subsidence away from the coast, which was predicted by having about a few cm of up-dip slope around 30-40 km depth in the plate boundary.

Figure 4: Results for SSE displacement and inter-SSE velocity.

Task 4: extract inter-SSE velocity

Using a temporally-averaged redundant stacking approach, and limit the interferograms in the stack to be only consisting of interferograms with temporal spans of 365 ± 20 days, we produced the inter-SSE event velocity stack and eventually used that to correct for the SSE stack to retrieve the SSE event displacement. The results are

shown in Figure 4 and four different profile lines are shown. We also compared these results with

GNSS-derived SSE displacement and inter-SSE velocity, which show overall good agreement (Figure 5)

Figure 5: Comparison between GNSS-derived SSE displacement and InSAR-derived SSE displacement (left two panels); Comparison between GNSS-derived inter-SSE velocity and InSAR-derived inter-SSE velocity (right two panels)

Figure 6 Preliminary uncertainty estimates for the InSAR-derived SSE displacement

Task 5: Modeling the SSE

This task is still in progress. We performed both two-dimensional and three-dimensional forward models and compared predictions from uniform 2 cm up-dip slip between 30 and 40 km depths with surface displacement from our GNSS as well as InSAR-derived SSE displacement and found that they agree broadly. We haven't finished the inversion part. We intend to pursue that in the next few

months. We plan to calculate the model resolution resulted from InSAR-derived SSE displacement and compare that with GNSS-derived SSE event displacement to understand better the advantage provided by the dense coverage of InSAR measurements. We also plan to include InSAR uncertainty into the inversion (Figure 6).

3. Opportunities for Training and Professional Development

This project provided training and professional development opportunities for Eshanta Mishra, who is currently completing his second year as a PhD student in the Department of Sustainable Earth System Sciences at UT Dallas. The project has served as the foundation for Eshanta's dissertation research. As part of his progress, he successfully passed his PhD qualifying exam on April 29, 2026.

4. Dissemination of Results to Communities of Interest

Results from this project were presented in multiple conferences listed below.

1. CRESCENT Annual Meeting held between November 27th and 30th, 2025, in Seattle, Washington. P.I. Zheng presented a poster presentation.
2. AGU Fall Meeting between December 15th and 19th, 2025 in New Orleans, Louisiana. Graduate Student Participant Eshanta Mishra presented a poster.
3. CRESCENT Spring Virtual Session – Updates on 2024-25 Seed Awards on April 21st, 2026. PI Zheng delivered a short talk.
4. IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS) between August 10th and 14th, 2026 in Washington DC. The graduate student participant Eshanta Mishra is expected to deliver an oral presentation and has an accepted conference paper.

5. What's next?

After wrapping up Task 5, we will prepare to submit a manuscript that summarizes the main findings from this seed grant.

In addition, we plan to use the results from this seed grant to pursue the FINNEST (Future Investigators in NASA Earth and Space Science and Technology) Award by NASA to support the graduate student researcher.

In particular, we would like to explore the recently launched NASA-ISRO SAR (NISAR) data over Cascadia. NISAR operates at L-band, which is expected to maintain better coherence over the heavily vegetated Cascadia region, as supported by our comparison between ALOS-2 and Sentinel-1 observations. Although both NISAR and ALOS-2 use L-band radar, NISAR offers a key advantage through its much more regular acquisition schedule. Specifically, NISAR is expected to acquire data over Cascadia every 12 days, a repeat interval that is critical for recovering small deformation signals associated with slow-slip events in this region.